

Photoelectrochemical Studies on Titanium Molybdate

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Titanium molybdate was prepared from solution phase. Its chemical composition was determined by estimating the metal contents. The material was characterised by X-ray diffraction, electrical conductivity and diffuse reflectance spectroscopy. The photoelectrochemical properties of titanium molybdate are reported. The flat-band potential is located at -0.53 V vs SCE. The conversion efficiency was found to be 0.04%.

THE photoelectrochemical (PEC) cells are attracting a great deal of attention for conversion of solar energy¹⁻⁴. However, the development of these cells have somewhat suffered by the relatively low conversion efficiency and poor stability offered by semiconductor electrode. Efforts are being made⁵⁻⁹ to develop an efficient PEC cell with stable semiconductor electrode.

The particularly important problem is selecting suitable photosensitive semiconductor electrodes. For effective solar energy conversion, one of the desirable properties of the semiconducting electrode is an appropriate energy band gap. In search of the most suitable photoanode material, many n-type semiconducting materials have been investigated^{5,9-11}.

We have studied titanium molybdate as part of a programme for evaluation of oxides materials for their PEC behaviour. In the present study, we report the preparation, characterisation and PEC properties of titanium molybdate.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

Equivalent amounts of a ammonium molybdate solution¹² was added to a solution of potassium titanium oxalate and the mixture was digested over a water-bath for 0.5 h to get precipitate of titanium(IV) molybdate and dried in an oven at 110°. The dry powder was finely ground in and mixed with 5% solution of polyvinyl acetate¹³ in acetone. About 2 ml solution per gram of powder¹⁴ was found to be fairly satisfactory for the purpose. The powder was then pressed to pellets of 1.2 cm diameter and fired at 700° for 30 h by the standard ceramic technique¹⁵.

The chemical composition of molybdate of titanium(IV) was determined by estimating its metal content¹⁶. Its formation was further confirmed by X-ray diffraction (XRD) study using a Philips PW 1700 diffractometer with $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation. The electrical resistivity in the range (298–550 K) was

measured using a BPL-India RM 160 MK IIIA megohmmeter. To achieve this a thin layer of colloidal graphite was applied on the clean and flat parallel faces of the pellet to provide good electrical contact. Diffuse reflectance spectra were recorded on a Varian DMS 80 spectrophotometer.

The pellets of titanium molybdate were sintered in hydrogen atmosphere at 500° for 2 h to enhance its electrical conductivity. The resistance of pellet was brought down to near about $10^2 \Omega$. The surface of the pellet was polished. The silver paste was applied on one surface of the pellet and fired at 300° for 1 h. The ohmic contact between copper wire and the silver coated surface was made and the surface was covered with epoxy. This electrode acted as photoanode.

The platinum cathode was fabricated by spot welding a platinum wire to a platinum plate (1 cm × 1 cm). The three-electrode PEC cell was designed

TABLE 1—X-RAY DIFFRACTION DATA OF TiMoO_6 *

d (observed) Å	Intensity (observed) I/I_0	hkl
4.669 1	51.4	(110)
4.260 2	42.2	(001)
3.579 4	59.5	(101)
3.301 5	80.0	(200)
3.149 7	100.0	(111)
2.613 1	52.0	(201)
2.429 0	24.9	(211)
2.337 2	51.9	(220)
2.090 1	25.0	(310)
2.028 9	25.1	(102)
1.956 8	52.4	(301)
1.876 0	99.2	(311)
1.792 1	42.6	(202)
1.770 1	35.1	(212)
1.683 9	24.8	(321)
1.575 1	51.5	(222)
1.533 1	12.0	(302)
1.492 9	79.8	(312)
1.420 9	25.0	(003)
1.389 5	24.8	(322)
1.360 2	25.0	(112)
1.305 1	65.0	(402)

*Symmetry : Tetragonal, $a_0 = 6.6078 \text{ \AA}$, $c_0 = 4.2646 \text{ \AA}$.

using titanium(IV) molybdate as photoanode, the platinum metal as counter electrode and a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) (Elico ER-70) as a reference electrode. A 150 W tungsten-halogen lamp was used as light source and illuminated through a quartz plate.

In all PEC measurements, 1 N NaOH was used as electrolyte. The capacitance-voltage and current-voltage characteristics of the cell were studied and the measurement procedures are described elsewhere¹⁷.

Results and Discussion

The percentage of Ti^{IV} present in titanium molybdate is found to be 19.27% against calculated 19.97%. XRD result shows that titanium molybdate crystallises in tetragonal system with lattice parameter $a_0 = 6.6078 \text{ \AA}$ and $c_0 = 4.2646 \text{ \AA}$. The crystallographic data are given in Table 1. On the basis of chemical analysis and XRD data, the molecular formula for titanium molybdate has been suggested to be TiMoO_6 .

Fig. 1 shows temperature dependence of the electrical conductivity of titanium molybdate. The variation of $\log \sigma$ against $1/T$ is linear showing that the exponential law $\sigma = \sigma_0 \exp(\Delta E/kT)$ is obeyed in the temperature range studied. The activation energy ΔE as calculated from the graph is 2.70 eV. Graph also indicates that TiMoO_6 is semiconducting in nature.

Reflectance spectra is an efficient tool for the determination of band gap of semiconductor¹⁸. The diffuse reflectance spectra of powdered titanium(IV) molybdate before and after hydrogen treatment were scanned (Fig. 2). It was observed that the nature of the reflectance spectra remained unchanged. The band gap was found to be 3.2 eV by this method. The difference in the values of band gap and activation energy determined from diffuse reflectance spectra and electrical conductivity

measurement respectively is attributed to different experimental conditions and the source of excitation of the electron.

Titanium molybdate showed a high resistivity ($10^8 \text{ } \Omega \text{ cm}$). In order to obtain the maximum

Fig. 1. Temperature dependence of electrical conductivity of TiMoO_6 .

Fig. 2. Reflectance spectra of TiMoO_6 powder.

photoresponse, the semiconductor electrode should have a low resistivity. Therefore, before utilising the pellet of titanium molybdate as photoanode in PEC cell, its resistivity must be decreased. This is achieved by sintering the pellets in hydrogen atmosphere which causes oxygen deficiency and forms discrete levels with in the band gap and makes available to capture electrons from the conduction band. The resistivity was brought down to nearly $10^3 \Omega \text{ cm}$. This value is rather high, but one has to maintain the mild reducing condition to prevent the formation of metallic titanium.

The semiconductor-electrolyte interface capacitance has been measured as a function of applied voltage at a frequency of 1 kHz. Assuming that the major contribution of the capacitance arises from space charge layer, the data is plotted on the Mott-Schottky relation,

$$\frac{1}{C^2} = \frac{2}{q \Sigma \epsilon_0 N_0} [V - V_{fb} - (kT/q)]$$

where, Σ is the dielectric constant of the space charge, ϵ_0 the permittivity of vacuum, N_0 the charge carrier density, V_{fb} the flat-band potential and V the applied electrode potential. A linear curve between $[1/C^2]$ and applied potential (Fig. 3) on extrapolation gave the value of flat-band potential -0.53 V vs SCE.

Fig. 3. Mott-Schottky plot of TiMoO_5 .

The maximum power efficiency and the fill factor were calculated from the $I-V$ characteristics of the PEC cell (Fig. 4). The photocurrent and photovoltage of the semiconductor electrode were measured at different biased potentials. The fill factor and power efficiency were calculated to be 0.22 and 0.04% respectively. The low power efficiency is due to comparatively high band gap of semiconductor⁹, high internal resistance of cell, polarisation and surface recombination centres on the electrode surface.

It is concluded from above studies that solar to electrical conversion efficiency is quite low. How-

Fig. 4. $I-V$ characteristics of TiMoO_5 photoanode.

ever, it is possible to fabricate PEC cell using pellet of titanium molybdate as photoanode in energy converter device.

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